

FULL PAPER

Title: Protection Of Vulnerable and Marginal sections of Society

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Introduction: In modern world wherein India sees itself as the fastest growing economy for its size, along with being the 6th richest economy in the world in process of being the 5th richest and wherein India also aspires to be the permanent member of United Nations Security Council, Indian track record in solving domestic issues amicably, Indian record for humanism in neighbourhood and how it solves the modern dilemma of balancing economic growth with sustainable development in keeping the balance between the native people, wildlife and sustainable goals is all the more relevant for the world to see learn and to respect India.

In India the marginalised and vulnerable groups take many forms which does include the tribes in forest land, the refugees from Myanmar in North East, the people who have called India their home for more than 40 years and bled for India...and who are now on the verge of losing their citizenship along with the vast vulnerable populace consisting of both the minorities and below poverty line people. This unique circumstance provides India both crisis and opportunity to be stronger, wiser and better as both a nation and as well as people.

Keywords tribal's , minorities, vulnerable section, refugees, citizenship, sustainable development and growth

Of course the author of the paper does recognise the fact that the problem in question is a very complex one and there is no silver bullet to solve all the issues at hand. The paper does try to make an attempt to initiate the efforts to solve the problems at hand.

Current Scenario: In the following paper the author shall be focussing on 4 aspects of minorities who are suffering in India and whose suffering also provides India an opportunity to rise as a responsible and humane country whose actions can very well set an example to the world to resolve their problems in an amicable manner. The 3 groups on whom the focus of the following paper is going to be are on: The tribals, The refugees, The people of north east who are on verge of losing their citizenship

Significance of protecting the aforesaid three groups:

I Problems and Concerns Scheduled Tribes and Scheduled Castes

Present Situation and Socio economic Problem

Although the scheduled tribe percentage in India is around 8.6%, they can play a very important role in ensuring sustainable growth and development in India. Even According to Sustainable development goals 2030, one of its goals is to ensure growth and improvement of

Indigenous People in focus achieving which plays a very important role in ensuring sustainable development in India.

Moreover, even according to world bank report, although indigenous people make up only 5% of the global population, they account for 15% of the world's poor.

In india it is more so pronounced. According to 2001 census, although sc and st comprise 16.2 percent and 8.2% respectively, yet 47.3% of India's poor are concentrated in these two groups.

Even according to 2011 census although 8% of Indian population comprises of about 8% of India's population, they account for a fourth of the population living in poorest wealth decile.

Thus, concentrating on helping uplifting the tribals is going to play a vital role in ensuring sustainable and inclusive growth and development of India's economic growth and development.

However, there are two legislations which have been recently passed which goes against the grain of ensuring the inclusive sustainable growth and development of the two classes at hand.

Forest Protection Act and precarious condition Of Scheduled Tribes

First move which has adversely affected the interests of the scheduled tribes was The Forest Act in adherence to which the Supreme Court had directed 17 states to evict the scheduled tribe members and forest dwellers, whose claims to Forest Rights Act had been rejected before July 27. This had put nearly 1 million people of tribals at the risk of eviction from various forest lands prescribed under the Scheduled Tribes and other Forest Dwellers (Recognitions of Forest rights) Act.

While 7,67,467 Scheduled Tribes claims were rejected, 4,45,047 Other Traditional Forest Dwellers claims were rejected in 17 states.

The tribals affected include around 60,000 people in Andhra Pradesh, 40,000 people in Kerala, 7000 in Tamil nadu and around 82,000 in Telangana.

The Center's apathy has created grave concerns for the tribal people which also defeats the purpose of having the act in the first place.

Several activists have pointed out that inaction of forest department officials in granting forest rights to these tribals and forest dwellers issuing land rights documents and other identity cards have been the root cause of the problem.

The greater irony lies in the fact that, if the tribals fail to produce the required documents not only they shall be evicted but they also will not be properly rehabilitated either.

There are two highly negative repercussions in taking away the tribals of their rightful land holdings, which are as follows:

1. Adds fuel to the fire of Naxalism and Subsequent Energy Crisis: The great Mao said if the communists are like fishes, then people are like water, without the active support of people communism or Maoism cannot exist.

Naxalism has been a bane to india's socio economic and political stability. Not only according to the Home Ministry Officials Naxal Violence has claimed 12,000 lives in 20 years (from 1998 to 2018), but even according to Coal India estimates, Maoists illegally mining and selling coal from coal india coalfields, has resulted a revenue loss of 600 cr rupees a year or a profit of 300 cr a year lost.

The Maoist insurgency has a direct bearing on fuel availability and infrastructural development in the country. Of India's capacity of 2,37,743 mega watts around 59% or 140 723.39 MW is fuelled by coal india. The illegal extraction of coal has resulted in 3 million tonne loss at the state run firm...this comes at a time when coal india has reported a shortfall of 20 million tonnes..

Demand for coal in india is projected to increase from around 650 mt to 730 mt a year in 2016-17, but projected availability is only 550mt a year.

Thus executing inhumane eviction of Scheduled tribe from their rightful land without proper rehabilitation, is not only going to fuel the ideologies of maoist violence but also is going to have a very adverse effect on our power generation as well.

Luckily the Supreme court on February 13 order directing 21 states to evict 11.8 lakh illegal forest dwellers whose claim has been rejected by the authorities.....has given a breather to the concerned group but however there should be adequate sustainable solution to ensure peace remains in Indian nation.

Negative Impact of Reservation to economically backward people(124th Amendment) on sc and st

There has always been a discontent that the continuance of reservation policy must be scrapped. Reservation policy although it in itself can't help in upliftment of poor people....in some way it does give the populace a chance on social mobility.

Moreover according to the UPSC report states that in 2014, only 0.14% applications to the upsc were selected. Moreover general category and OBC's have the highest success rate, about 0.17% and SC's have the lowest, about 0.08%.

Thus either ending reservation or prolonging reservation is not the adequate solution for the empowerment of people. Additionally on top of it, reserving 10%, in the name of economic backwardness to people whose annual income is less than 8 lakh or 66000 per month which according to Indian Human Development Survey covers around 95% of population is not necessarily a wise move.

Moreover, this shall also reduce the sc,st and obc's claim as previously they could also apply on this reserved general category.

II. Problems and concerns of Rohingya Refugees

The issue of rohingya crisis is the one which has been decades in the making which has led to concerns over the plight of thousands of muslims who do form a minority in the rakhine state. Myanmar does not recognise these people as their citizens as they do believe that these people re illegal migrants from the Bangladesh.

Recent violence in Rakhine state has displaced several hundred thousand Rohingyas within Myanmar and driven out some 7,00,000 of them to neighbouring Bangladesh after the military launched a bloody crackdown triggered by military attacks on security posts in late August 2017.

The UN has described the violence against the Rohingya Crisis as the textbook act of violence of ethnic cleansing. In November 2017, Myanmar and Bangladesh signed an agreement on repatriation of refugees. In late May 2018, Myanmar signed an agreement with the UN to allow hundreds and thousands of Rohingyas to “return safely and by choice”.

The international community have urged Myanmar to speed up the process of repatriation, though concerns remain..

India’s response to Rohingya crisis has evolved swiftly:

1st Phase: In first phase that began with eruption of violent conflicts between Rakhine Buddhists and Rohingya Muslims in Rakhine state in 2012, Delhi considered it an ‘internal affair’ but was sympathetic to Myanmar.

In 2014, the new Govt. tacitly endorsed the position of former Govt. In 2015, the Rohingya problem assumed regional dimension when Thailand, Malaysia and Indonesia all turned away overcrowded boats carrying Rohingyas attempting to land on their shores.

Factors which influenced Delhi’s position in the first phase are as follows:

1. Public denunciation of Myanmar would have pushed Myanmar towards China.
2. Some of Indian Companies had economic interests in Shwe gas field.
3. India also had connectivity interest to join its landlocked north east with the Bay Of Bengal through Rakhine state

2nd Phase: There were calls for Delhi to help Rohingyas...however Delhi decided to look otherway around. This phase started in around 2017, when New Delhi started focussing on deporting the “illegal migrants” who had increased from around 10,500 in 2015 to 40,000 in the following years. India also initiated “Operation Insaniyat” to ensure relief assistance to the Rohingya refugees who were in Bangladeshi camps.

New Delhi started addressing the Rohingya refugees in Bangladesh as “Displaced persons” and the same persons present in India as “illegal immigrants”

3rd Phase: this phase began after China stepped down from its “3 step solution” to resolve the crisis. India did not want to let any other regional power to leverage the situation at the cost of its own interests.

Under the MOU, India pledged, US \$ 25 million for a five year development project in Rakhine state. India joined UNSC delegation that visited Myanmar in early May 2018 in which India stressed the importance of “ safe speedy and sustainable return of displaced persons to Rakhine State”

In the meantime, a plea was filed in Supreme Court by two Rohingya immigrants- Mohammad Salimullah and Mohammad Shaqir- who claimed they took refuge in India after escaping Myanmar due to widespread discrimination, violence and bloodshed against their community in Myanmar.

The Supreme Court on Friday adjourned the Rohingya case till January 2019 for final disposal which is yet to be heard.

III National Register Citizens on India:

Assam is one of the several states seriously suffering from the problem of illegal immigrants who generally are Bangladeshis. Though the exercise over National Register of Citizens (NRC) for Assam is being undertaken under the supervision of the Supreme Court, there may be serious doubts about its effective implementation.

Ever since the NRC's second and final draft was published leaving out 40,07,707 people in Assam from its list, the issue has got politicised.

Deportation To Bangladesh?

The NRC is scheduled to hear the appeals of these 40 lakh people in August and September. It will publish the final list on December 31.

Even if the final figure is half of what it is now, it would be extremely difficult for the Centre to deport them to Bangladesh.

The neighbouring country has already made its intention clear by stating that this is an internal issue of Assam and India and it has nothing to do with it.

Bangladesh's government stand has been that the people belong to neighbouring states of India.

Discrepancies

There have been several anomalies in the NRC....as sometimes we find that one of the twins name being missed or at other times we do see that the name of mother being there but child being missing.

In such a scenario as this, it would become very difficult for the government to either separate the families to effectively implement the policy.

Tensions Building up in midst of communities

The implementation of NRC may lead to serious law and order problem not just in Assam but also in other parts of India.

Most of those left out are Muslims. They might feel persecuted under the current political dispensation. This divisive politics may lead to building up of tensions.

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Voting

As of now, it has come to being that Election Commission has decided that names of the people which have been excluded in the NRC do have the right to vote in the elections as such.

Properties

The left out will not be entitled to buy land or a house in the country.

But the government will be hard-pressed to retrieve pieces of land and houses from people who have already got them registered in their names.

Even if the government succeeds in achieving this daunting task, it may fail to stop people from buying benami properties which are quite common in the country.

Measures which can be taken on the given three front to ensure the unity and integrity of our nation and also as to the importance of taking the relevant measures:

ADIVASI AND TRADITIONAL FOREST DWELLERS

1. Saving the rights of people especially those of scheduled caste and scheduled tribes ensures sustainable growth and development in India along with political stability

Since 1980, through the Forest Conservation Act (FCA), the Ministry of Environment, Forest and Climate Change (MoEF) has “diverted for non-forest use” (bureaucratese for destroyed) over 1.5 million hectares of forest.

On February 13th the honourable supreme court gave an order as per Forest Rights Act 2006 to evict in total 1.8 million people, and luckily on February 28th the honourable supreme court stayed the order on the same.

However, the irony lies in the fact that 2016, for instance, a proposal whereby the Odisha Mining Corporation (OMC) sought 1,400 acres of forestland across seven Adivasi villages of Keonjhar in the ecologically sensitive Gandhamardan mountains, for an iron ore mine. The diversion proposal sent by the OMC and the Odisha government to the MoEF included seven copycat gram sabha resolutions, supposedly representing the seven villages. Each identical resolution depicted villagers, over 2,000 in all, as saying they were not using the forests for cultivation, house-building or any livelihood, had no individual or community claims to it, and that they “request” the government to implement the forest diversion. In the villages, these resolutions evoked shock and rage. Residents reported to the researcher (a journalist of a reputed national newspaper) that they were fake.

After Chitragada Choudhry’s news report on the case in 2016, the MoEF asked the State government to probe the matter. What followed is a telling comment on forest governance. The probe report, neither shared with villagers nor made public, glossed over testimonies it gathered of 11 villagers. On how all seven gram sabha resolutions could be identical, officials said, “This may have been done as the same officials conducted the meetings in all villages, and the agenda of the meetings was also the same.” Effectively, the OMC, abetted by officials, created resolutions tailored for forest diversion, thus emptying the gram sabhas’ free informed consent powers of any substantive meaning. Last October, despite letters by villages about the forgery and pending FRA claims, the MoEF issued permission to the OMC to destroy this stretch of forest.

Due to such lackadaisical Economic growth and development although India’s ranking in the “Ease of doing business report published by the world bank there has been a drastic improvement in ranking from 134 to 77 in past 4 years, India has seen its ranking in Environmental degradation plummet to 177 of 180 in Environmental performance index released in 2019.

Moreover according to air quality Index, it has also been found out that out of the 20 most polluted cities in the world 15 are actually found in India.

Moreover recent world bank report focussing on sustainable development with reference to India also pointed out that, India allowing indigenous people (Adivasis) and Traditional forest users to use firewood, would most certainly play a vital role in reducing forest fire.

So to ensure that we have sustainable growth and development it is very much essential to :

1. Empower Gram Sabhas

2. Acknowledge the fact that adivasis have an important role to play in the sustainable development of the Forest land which hopefully shall be taken into consideration by the supreme court in its upcoming judgement of July 2019.
3. While removing adivasis and traditional forest dwellers from forests in case of legitimate concerns, then no stone should be left unturned to ensure that they are gracefully rehabilitated regardless of the fact that they have paper documentation or lacking, all onus must be on the govt. Officials to ensure that the said people are not adivasis or traditional forest dwellers and not the other way round.
This will most certainly help in subduing the ill will of the displaced people which in turn was being wrongly exploited by the naxals to meet their own ends.
4. More importantly freedom of speech and expression must be respected and learned intellectuals like RamChandra Guha, Romilla Thappar Arundhati Roy and the like must not be addressed as “urban naxals” and Anti nationalslegislations must be passed to ensure that the intellectuals are sure that they have freedom to speak their mind out.
Moreover one should realise that only when the problem is recognised, only then the problem can be solved.

ROHINGYAS

India needs to find a way out to balance its security needs on one hand and on the other hand its reputation as well as responsibility of being the largest democracy in the Asian subcontinent.

As of now till supreme court verdict comes out nothing can be said.....however the one thing Indian Government must strictly refrain from doing is that it must not pass an amendment bill in future that is blatantly biased or discriminatory on the basis of religion.

If India gives amnesty it must be for all refugees or if India tries to settle the same people back safely in Myanmar, it must be for everyone. Secularism and even handed legislations and acts can only protect the idea of India for which our founding fathers made the ultimate sacrifice.

National Registry for Citizens

For the people who have spent more than 30 years in India Govt atleast now must allow them to stay in India and must take measures that from now onwards people are not allowed in.

For this measure obviously, the north eastern states shall have their opposition, so the Indians who have been in India for 30 years must be allowed to enter in mainland India.

The author is giving this solution based on two circumstances and one clause:

First Circumstance: These people whose names are not even in the NRC are allowed to vote provided their names are in the Electoral Rolls by this logic tacitly we are admitting that they are our citizens.

Second Circumstance: The Government of Bangladesh has already given the statement that in no circumstance will it take any people from India. Moreover mainland Indians could also be convinced by the fact of historical legacy pointing out that the Bangladeshi's for 2 millennia's have been part of India

Clause: India should have state of the art border security to ensure that illegal migrants do not enter India.

Conclusion: In India the marginalised and vulnerable groups take many forms which does include the tribes in forest land, the refugees from Myanmar in North East, the people who have called India their home for more than 40 years and bled for India...and who are now on the verge of losing their citizenship along with the vast vulnerable populace consisting of both the minorities and below poverty line people. This unique circumstance provides India both crisis and opportunity to be stronger, wiser and better as both a nation and as well as people. Thus India should show the courage to take the wise decision and set an example for the world to emulate.

Sources:

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